

1 First measurement of the $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ production in PbPb
2 collisions with the CMS experiment*

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7 The observation of the τ lepton pair production in ultraperipheral nucleus-
8 nucleus collisions, a pure quantum electrodynamics (QED) process, is pre-
9 sented. The measurement is based on a data sample collected by the CMS
10 experiment at a per nucleon center-of-mass energy of 5.02 TeV, and corre-
11 sponding to an integrated luminosity of $404 \mu\text{b}^{-1}$. The photon-induced
12 $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ production is observed with a statistical significance of at
13 least five standard deviations in a decay process involving one muon and
14 three particles identified as charged pions in the final state. The cross
15 section is measured in a fiducial phase space region, and is found to be
16 $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-) = 4.8 \pm 0.6 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.5 \text{ (syst)} \mu\text{b}$, in agreement with leading-
17 order QED predictions. The $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-)$ measurement is used to de-
18 termine for the first time the anomalous magnetic moment of the τ lep-
19 ton a_τ , which is currently poorly constrained. This approach can be used
20 to produce constraints on a_τ that surpass the current best from previous
21 lepton-lepton colliders.

22 **1. Introduction**

23 One of the contributing factors in the couplings of leptons (ℓ) with pho-
24 tons (γ) is the anomalous magnetic moments $a_\ell = (g - 2)_\ell/2$, with the
25 g -factor being the proportionality constant that relates the magnetic mo-
26 ment to the spin of the lepton. Ultraperipheral collisions (UPC) of heavy
27 ions provide an extremely clean environment [1] to probe a_τ [2] at the LHC,
28 and hence offering ample room for searching for physics beyond the standard
29 model.

30 Here, we present [3] an observation of photoproduction of pairs of τ lep-
31 tons in lead-lead (PbPb) collisions $\text{PbPb}(\gamma\gamma) \rightarrow \text{Pb}^{(*)} + \text{Pb}^{(*)} \tau^+\tau^-$ (here-
32 after referred to as $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$). As shown in Fig. 1, the τ leptons are

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33 reconstructed in a decay process involving in the final state one muon and
 34 three particles (“prongs”) identified as charged pions (π) over a fiducial
 35 phase space region defined by the muon and pion transverse momenta (p_T)
 36 and their pseudorapidities (η). The ATLAS Collaboration has also reported
 37 a measurement of $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ using a larger PbPb data sample with an in-
 38 tegrated luminosity of 1.44 nb^{-1} [4, 5].

Fig. 1. Leading-order QED diagram for the photoproduction of a pair of τ leptons $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ in ultraperipheral PbPb collisions. The presence of $\gamma\tau\tau$ vertices gives enhanced sensitivity to the anomalous electromagnetic couplings of the τ lepton; here, the anomalous magnetic moment a_τ is highlighted [3].

39 2. Event selection, signal and background estimation

40 The analysis is based on a data sample collected by the CMS exper-
 41 iment [6] at a per nucleon center-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02 \text{ TeV}$ in
 42 2015, and corresponding to an integrated luminosity of $404 \mu\text{b}^{-1}$. We filter
 43 UPC events by requiring in real time (“online”) a single muon with no p_T
 44 threshold requirement and minimum event activity above the noise thresh-
 45 old in the forward hadron (HF) calorimeter ($3.0 < |\eta| < 5.2$). For the “ τ_μ ”
 46 candidate, an offline cut is applied on its pseudorapidity to be $|\eta| < 2.4$ and
 47 is required to be labeled as “soft” [7]. The requirement on the transverse
 48 momentum varies, depending on its $|\eta|$, and is $p_T > 3.5 \text{ GeV}$ for $|\eta| < 1.2$
 49 and $p_T > 2.5 \text{ GeV}$ for $|\eta| \geq 1.2$. The tracks forming the “ $\tau_{3\text{prong}}$ ” candidate
 50 are identified as charged pions by the particle-flow algorithm, required to
 51 be within the tracker acceptance ($|\eta| < 2.5$), and close longitudinally and
 52 vertically to the primary vertex. The minimum transverse momentum is
 53 0.5 (0.3) GeV for the leading- and subleading- p_T pions, respectively. The
 54 selected tracks are also required to be labeled as “high-purity” [8] tracks.
 55 The $\tau_{3\text{prong}}$ candidate is then required to be of opposite charge relative to

56 the selected τ_μ , and to have $p_T^{\text{vis}} > 2 \text{ GeV}$, where p_T^{vis} is the vector sum p_T of
 57 the three pions. Additionally, the visible invariant mass of $\tau_{3\text{prong}}$ candidate
 58 is required to be less than 1.5 GeV.

Fig. 2. Left: Invariant mass of the three pions forming the $\tau_{3\text{prong}}$ candidate. Right: Difference in azimuthal opening angle between the τ_μ and $\tau_{3\text{prong}}$ candidates. In both cases, the signal component (magenta histogram) is stacked on top of the background component (green histogram), considering their prefit (left) or postfit (right) normalizations. The sum of signal and background is displayed by a blue line and the shaded area shows the statistical uncertainty (left) or the total uncertainty in the postfit prediction (right). The data are represented with black points and the uncertainty is statistical only. The lower panels show the ratios of data to the signal-plus-background prediction, and the shaded bands represent the statistical uncertainty in the prefit expectation (left) or postfit prediction (right).

59 A dedicated $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ [9] Monte Carlo (MC) sample is generated
 60 with MADGRAPH5_aMC@NLO (v2.6.5) [10], decayed and hadronized with
 61 PYTHIA8 (v2.1.2) [11], and simulated by GEANT4 [12] to study the detector
 62 effects. Background contamination is estimated in a data-driven way, using
 63 the so-called “ABCD method”, in which the four uncorrelated phase space
 64 regions are defined based on the number of tracks per event and the HF
 65 activity. In all cases, good agreement is observed between the measured
 66 distributions and the sum of the signal simulation and background estima-
 67 tion, *e.g.*, as shown in Fig. 2 (left) for the invariant mass of the $\tau_{3\text{prong}}$
 68 candidate.

69 3. Results

70 A binned maximum likelihood method is used for the signal extrac-
 71 tion. The difference in opening azimuthal angle between the τ_μ and $\tau_{3\text{prong}}$

72 leptons, $\Delta\phi(\tau_\mu, \tau_{3\text{prong}})$, is used as the final discriminant. Systematic uncer-
 73 tainties may affect the normalization and the shape of the $\Delta\phi(\tau_\mu, \tau_{3\text{prong}})$
 74 distribution and these uncertainties are represented by nuisance parameters
 75 in the fit. The total uncertainty, found to be 9.7%, is their sum in quadra-
 76 ture taking into account correlations in the fit procedure. To compare the
 77 compatibility of the data with the background-only and signal plus back-
 78 ground hypotheses, where the signal is allowed to be scaled by some factor
 79 r , we construct a test statistic based on the profile likelihood ratio. The best
 80 fit value of the signal strength is given by the minimum, which corresponds
 81 to $r = 0.99^{+0.16}_{-0.14}$ and the signal events of $N_{\text{sig}} = 77 \pm 12$. The post-fit $\Delta\phi(\tau_\mu,$
 82 $\tau_{3\text{prong}})$ distribution is shown in Fig. 2 (right).

83 The cross section $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-)$ is measured in the fiducial phase space
 84 region, following the kinematic requirements previously described. The for-
 85 mula used is $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-) = N_{\text{sig}}/(2\epsilon\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}\mathcal{B}_{\tau_\mu}\mathcal{B}_{\tau_{3\text{prong}}})$, where N_{sig} is the
 86 number of signal events estimated by the fit process, $\epsilon = (78.5 \pm 0.8)\%$
 87 is the total signal efficiency, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = 404 \pm 20 \mu\text{b}^{-1}$ the total integrated lu-
 88 minosity, and $\mathcal{B}_{\tau_\mu} = (17.39 \pm 0.04)\%$ and $\mathcal{B}_{\tau_{3\text{prong}}} = (14.55 \pm 0.06)\%$ [2]
 89 the branching fractions for the two τ lepton decay modes. Combining all
 90 of the above, the fiducial cross section is found to be $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-) =$
 91 4.8 ± 0.6 (stat) ± 0.5 (syst) μb . The result, summarized in Fig. 3, is com-
 92 pared to leading-order QED predictions [9, 13]. Further assuming the cor-
 93 rection factor of Ref. [9] to extrapolate the fiducial cross section measure-
 94 ment to the full phase space region, we then use the dependence of the total
 95 $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-)$ as a function of a_τ to extract the model-dependent value of
 96 $a_\tau = 0.001^{+0.055}_{-0.089}$.

97 4. Summary

98 In summary, the observation of the τ lepton pair production in ultra-
 99 peripheral nucleus-nucleus collisions is reported. Events with one muon
 100 and three particles identified as charged pions in the final state are recon-
 101 structed from a lead-lead data sample collected by the CMS experiment at
 102 $\sqrt{s_{\text{NN}}} = 5.02$ TeV in 2015, and corresponding to an integrated luminosity
 103 of $404 \mu\text{b}^{-1}$. This measurement introduces a novel experimental strategy
 104 using heavy ion data recorded by the LHC in order to measure the τ lepton
 105 magnetic moment a_τ . This approach can be used to produce constraints on
 106 a_τ that surpass the current best from previous lepton-lepton colliders.

Fig. 3. The cross section, $\sigma(\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-)$, measured in a fiducial phase space region at $\sqrt{s_{\text{NN}}} = 5.02 \text{ TeV}$. The theoretical predictions [9, 13] are computed with leading-order accuracy in QED and are represented by the vertical solid lines that can be compared with the vertical dotted line representing this measurement. The outer blue (inner red) error bars surrounding the data point indicate the total (statistical) uncertainties, whereas the green hatched bands correspond to the uncertainty in the theoretical predictions as described in the main text. The potential electromagnetic excitation of the outgoing Pb ions is denoted by (*).

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- 110 [1] P. A. Steinberg for the ALICE, ATLAS, CMS, LHCb, and STAR
111 Collaborations, “Ultrapерipheral collisions at RHIC and the LHC”, *Nucl.*
112 *Phys. A* **1005** (2021) 122007, [doi:10.1016/j.nuclphysa.2020.122007](#).
- 113 [2] Particle Data Group Collaboration, “Review of Particle Physics”, *PTEP*
114 **2020** (2020) 083C01, [doi:10.1093/ptep/ptaa104](#).
- 115 [3] CMS Collaboration, “Observation of τ lepton pair production in
116 ultraperipheral lead-lead collisions at $\sqrt{s_{\text{NN}}} = 5.02 \text{ TeV}$ ”, (2022).
117 [arXiv:2206.05192](#). Submitted to *Phys. Rev. Lett.*
- 118 [4] ATLAS Collaboration, “Observation of the $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau\tau$ process in PbPb
119 collisions and constraints on the τ lepton anomalous magnetic moment with
120 the ATLAS detector”, (2022). [arXiv:2204.13478](#). Submitted to *Phys. Rev.*
121 *Lett.*
- 122 [5] I. Grabowska-Bold (On behalf of the ATLAS Collaboration), “ATLAS
123 measurements of photon-photon fusion processes in PbPb collisions”, in
124 *XXIX International Workshop on Deep-Inelastic Scattering and Related*
125 *Subjects (DIS2022)*. 2022. These proceedings.

- 126 [6] CMS Collaboration, “The CMS Experiment at the CERN LHC”, *JINST* **3**
127 (2008) S08004, doi:[10.1088/1748-0221/3/08/S08004](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/3/08/S08004).
- 128 [7] CMS Collaboration, “Performance of the CMS muon detector and muon
129 reconstruction with proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV”, *JINST* **13**
130 (2018) P06015, doi:[10.1088/1748-0221/13/06/P06015](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/13/06/P06015),
131 [arXiv:1804.04528](https://arxiv.org/abs/1804.04528).
- 132 [8] CMS Collaboration, “Description and performance of track and
133 primary-vertex reconstruction with the CMS tracker”, *JINST* **9** (2014)
134 P10009, doi:[10.1088/1748-0221/9/10/P10009](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/9/10/P10009), [arXiv:1405.6569](https://arxiv.org/abs/1405.6569).
- 135 [9] L. Beresford and J. Liu, “New physics and $\tau g - 2$ using LHC heavy ion
136 collisions”, *Phys. Rev. D* **102** (2020) 113008,
137 doi:[10.1103/PhysRevD.102.113008](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.102.113008), [arXiv:1908.05180](https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.05180). [Erratum:
138 doi:[10.1103/PhysRevD.106.039902](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.106.039902)].
- 139 [10] J. Alwall et al., “The automated computation of tree-level and
140 next-to-leading order differential cross sections, and their matching to parton
141 shower simulations”, *JHEP* **07** (2014) 079,
142 doi:[10.1007/JHEP07\(2014\)079](https://doi.org/10.1007/JHEP07(2014)079), [arXiv:1405.0301](https://arxiv.org/abs/1405.0301).
- 143 [11] T. Sjöstrand et al., “An introduction to PYTHIA 8.2”, *Comput. Phys.*
144 *Commun.* **191** (2015) 159, doi:[10.1016/j.cpc.2015.01.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2015.01.024),
145 [arXiv:1410.3012](https://arxiv.org/abs/1410.3012).
- 146 [12] GEANT4 Collaboration, “GEANT4—a simulation toolkit”, *Nucl. Instrum.*
147 *Meth. A* **506** (2003) 250, doi:[10.1016/S0168-9002\(03\)01368-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002(03)01368-8).
- 148 [13] M. Dyndal, M. Klusek-Gawenda, M. Schott, and A. Szczurek, “Anomalous
149 electromagnetic moments of τ lepton in $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ reaction in PbPb
150 collisions at the LHC”, *Phys. Lett. B* **809** (2020) 135682,
151 doi:[10.1016/j.physletb.2020.135682](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physletb.2020.135682), [arXiv:2002.05503](https://arxiv.org/abs/2002.05503).